

Manila – OpenStack File Sharing Service

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Project Specification

The CERN Computer Centre is host to 25,000 processors, adding up to more than 140,000 cores. In order to efficiently fulfil the computing demands of its users, the IT infrastructure is cloud oriented, offering the CERN Private Cloud, an Infrastructure-as-a-Service solution integrated with CERN's computing facilities.

The private cloud is based on OpenStack, the popular open source cloud-computing software platform. The system makes use of commodity hardware as its main source for computing and is tied in with several other services, such as networking and authentication.

Due to the ever-increasing computing needs at CERN, the private cloud also needs to be easily adaptable and extensible. One such computing need is the use of file-based network attached storage and network-shared file systems within the cloud in a self-service manner. In OpenStack, this has been addressed in 2012 with the start of the Manila project, meant to fill the empty space between block storage systems and object storage systems, bringing file-based storage systems to the discussion.

The scope of the project is to deploy OpenStack Manila within the CERN private cloud, configure it to work on commodity hardware, in correlation with the other existing services and also to document the appropriate findings.

Abstract

The report presents a short overview on what OpenStack is, how and why is it used at CERN and also goes into detail about the OpenStack Manila component, a service that enables file based storage and file sharing within OpenStack virtual machines.

OpenStack Manila is a relatively new OpenStack component, having started in 2012 and in 2014 it has reached the latest cycle of development, where it could still be found at the time of the report. The fundamental object Manila works with is the ‘share’, a unit of storage that can be accessed through the network simultaneously by multiple users. The scope of Manila is to provision shares in a ‘Shares-as-a-Service’ fashion, allowing entrusted users to manage their own shares independently, without the need of any external assistance, such as from an admin.

The scope of the project has been to experiment with this technology and assert its functionality in the context of the existing cloud at CERN. The report details the principal services and operation of OpenStack Manila, along with the most common used command lines. It also goes into detail about two ways in which Manila can be installed, either manually or by using a deployment automation tool. A look at the required configuration parameters is also presented.

In the last part, the deployed Manila service at CERN is presented, together with the configuration options used for the backend, the part responsible with linking the Manila service to the actual storage platform used.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	Motivation for Shared File System Service	6
2	OpenStack	7
2.1	Overview	7
2.2	OpenStack Components	7
2.3	OpenStack at CERN	8
3	Manila	9
3.1	Overview	9
3.2	Manila Architecture	9
3.3	Manila terminology	10
3.3.1	Share	10
3.3.2	Backend	10
3.3.3	Driver	10
3.3.4	Share Type	10
3.3.5	Share Access Rules	11
3.3.6	Share Network	11
3.3.7	Share Server	11
3.4	Manila network plugins	11
3.4.1	Standalone Network Plugin	11
3.4.2	Nova Network Plugin	12
3.4.3	Neutron Network Plugin	12
3.5	Manila CLI	12
4	Deployment of OpenStack	14
4.1	Using Packstack to install OpenStack	14
4.2	Manila integration	14
4.2.1	Step-by-step install guide	14
4.2.2	Configuration file	17
4.2.3	Using Packstack to install Manila	18
4.2.4	Manila-UI plugin for Horizon	19

5	Manila implementation	20
5.1	Generic driver - handling share servers.....	20
5.2	Generic driver - not handling share servers.....	21
5.3	Creating shares.....	22
6	Debugging information	23
6.1	Status of a share	23
6.2	Mounting NFS shares with caching enabled	23
6.3	Device mapping inconsistency.....	23
7	Conclusions	24
	References.....	25

1 Introduction

At CERN, the IT policy is to have all server machines hosted on the CERN OpenStack Infrastructure, also known as the CERN Private Cloud. The cloud structure has the great advantage that it can provide great resources from commodity hardware, which is more easily available. However, the software platform to support such a system is very complex, in this case, being implemented via OpenStack.

The private cloud must always adapt to the needs of its users while at the same time keeping up to date with the latest cloud computing techniques and OpenStack software versions. One such need was having an easily accessible file-sharing service within the private cloud. In order to achieve this, integrating the Manila component of OpenStack was proposed.

1.1 Motivation for Shared File System Service

In the current state of the system, the private cloud implements as one of its services the OpenStack Cinder component, responsible for offering block storage support. However, block-level protocols do not have any inherent locking or synchronisation process built-in, which makes sharing the same volume between multiple hosts a difficult task. In order to facilitate file sharing between virtual machines, external systems must be installed. This can burden the administration of the system and make the use of the service inconvenient for the user.

Introducing the OpenStack Manila component, file-based storage and file-sharing capabilities will be offered in a self-service way, following the Infrastructure-as-a-Service paradigm. The advantages of this, from the user perspective, would be being able to easily create new shared drives between multiple virtual machines in a similar manner to how the rest of the OpenStack services are used, via the command line interface in a familiar fashion or through the web interface.

2 OpenStack

The OpenStack project is an open source cloud computing platform for all types of clouds, which aims to be simple to implement, massively scalable and feature rich. Developers and cloud computing technologists from around the world create the OpenStack project.

2.1 Overview

OpenStack allows for the deployment and management of a cloud in the form of Infrastructure-as-a-Service solution through a set of interrelated services. Each service offers an application programming interface that facilitates this integration. It fulfils two main requirements: massive scalability and simplicity of implementation.

The platform is highly configurable, depending on your needs. The user can choose whether or not to implement several services offered by the software. The configuration of each component is also up to the user and is easily made through the application programming interface the tool provides. Therefore, there are many different ways to use OpenStack, which makes it a flexible tool that is able to work along with other software.

Figure 1 OpenStack Software Diagram

2.2 OpenStack Components

The OpenStack components you choose have a significant impact on the overall design. There are certain components that are always present (e.g. the Compute and Identity service) while the deployment of other components is left up to the choice of the system administrator.

The OpenStack community is very active and a new release of OpenStack occurs every 6 months. In the current version, code named Kilo, the following are considered to be fully integrated components:

- **Compute** (Nova): designed to automate the creation and managing of virtual machines, stands as the core of OpenStack.
- **Networking** (Neutron): manages the networking associated with OpenStack clouds.
- **Object Storage** (Swift): a fully distributed object storage platform that can be integrated into applications or used for backup and archiving.
- **Block Storage** (Cinder): provides persistent block-level storage for use with the compute instances.
- **Identity** (Keystone): primary tool for user authentication and role-based access control in OpenStack clouds.
- **Image Service** (Glance): provides discovery, registration and delivery services for disk and server images.
- **Dashboard** (Horizon): provides administrators and users a graphical interface to access and manage cloud-based resources.
- **Telemetry** (Ceilometer): measures usage and performance data across the services deployed in an OpenStack cloud.
- **Orchestration** (Heat): allows application developers to describe and automate the deployment of infrastructure.
- **Database** (Trove): allows users to quickly and easily make use of the features of a relational database.
- **Data Processing** (Sahara): provides simple means to provision a data-intensive application cluster.
- **Bare Metal Provisioning** (Ironic): aims to provision bare metal machines instead of virtual machines.

2.3 OpenStack at CERN

The IT policy at CERN is to have all server machines hosted on the CERN Private Cloud, which is based on a deployment of OpenStack and configured to be integrated with the CERN network and authentication services. To fulfil the demands of the users, the Private Cloud is administered by the Operating systems and Information Services (IT-OIS) group and is subject to constant change and improvements.

Out of the listed OpenStack components, the Private Cloud implements the Compute, Block Storage, Identity, Image Service, Telemetry, Dashboard and Orchestration, with plans of integrating the Neutron component. A similar plan was looking into the Manila component and asserting whether it would be valuable for the current configuration.

3 Manila

OpenStack Manila is a community-driven open source project meant to facilitate file-based storage and to provide a file-sharing service within an OpenStack cloud environment, effectively offering Shares-as-a-Service.

3.1 Overview

The Manila project was started in 2012 and developed as a fork of the Cinder project, as many of the concepts and API calls were anticipated to share much in common between file shares and volumes. Since then, the project has evolved, reaching incubation status, the latest cycle of development before becoming a full core project, in August 2014. Although Manila is available in the Kilo release of OpenStack, it is not yet integrated as a core component.

The File Share Service prototype provides coordinated access to shared or distributed file systems, in a similar manner to how Cinder provides its service. It allows the users to provision and manage CIFS and/or NFS within an OpenStack infrastructure. While the primary consumption of file shares would be across OpenStack Compute instances, the service is also intended to be accessible as an independent capability in line with the modular design established by other OpenStack services.

The reasoning for Manila was based on the desire to move applications into a private cloud, enclosing all the necessary services for them to function properly, but without specific accommodation for shared file systems, this was an incomplete solution.

3.2 Manila Architecture

The file sharing service has an architecture in line with the vision behind OpenStack: scalability and ease of implementation. It is composed of three services, a messaging bus and a database used for storing information.

The manila-api service is an application that accepts and validates REST requests from clients and routes them to other Manila processes as appropriate over the Messaging Bus.

The manila-scheduler service determines which backend should serve as the destination for a share creation request. It maintains non-persistent state for pools and backends, such as available capacity and supported extra specs. The algorithm utilized by the scheduler can be changed through the Manila configuration.

The manila-share accepts requests from other Manila processes and serves as the operation container for Manila drivers. This process is multi-threaded and typically has one thread of execution per Manila backend.

Figure 2 OpenStack Manila Architecture

3.3 Manila terminology

For clarity, the terminology associated with the Manila service that will be used throughout the report is explained.

3.3.1 Share

A Manila share is the fundamental resource unit allocated by the Shared File System service. It represents an allocation of a persistent, readable and writable filesystem that can be accessed by OpenStack compute instances, or clients outside of OpenStack. The underlying connection between the consumer of the share and the Manila service providing the share can be achieved with a variety of protocols, including NFS and CIFS.

Manila shares can be identified uniquely through a UUID assigned by the Manila service at the time of share creation. A Manila share may also be optionally referred to by a human-readable name, though this string is not guaranteed to be unique within a single tenant or deployment of Manila.

3.3.2 Backend

A Manila backend is the configuration object that represents a single provider of resource pools upon which provisioning requests for shared file systems may be fulfilled. A Manila backend communicates with the storage system through a Manila driver. Manila supports multiple backends to be configured and managed simultaneously.

A single Manila backend may be defined in the default section of the Manila configuration file, however, it is recommended that the `enabled_share_backends` configuration option be set to a comma-separated list of backend names and each backend have its own configuration stanza with the same name as listed in the aforementioned option.

3.3.3 Driver

A Manila driver is a particular implementation of a Manila backend that maps the abstract APIs and primitives of Manila to appropriate constructs within the particular storage solution underpinning the Manila backend.

In other words, the Manila driver implementation provides provisioning and other manipulation of storage devices but does not lay in the path of data I/O.

3.3.4 Share Type

A Manila share type is an abstract collection of criteria used to characterize Manila shares. The collection of criteria is specified as a list of key/value pairs, which are inspected by the Manila scheduler when determining which resource pools are able to fulfill a provisioning request.

3.3.5 Share Access Rules

Share access rules define which clients can access a particular Manila share. Access rules can be declared for NFS shares by listing the valid IPP networks (using CIDR notation) or particular IP addresses which should have access to the share. In the case of CIFS shares, the Windows security identifier can be specified.

3.3.6 Share Network

A share network is an object that defines a relationship between a tenant's network/subnet (as defined in an OpenStack network service: Neutron or Nova-Network) and the Manila shares created by the same tenant. One example usage of a share network would be the desire to provision shares that will be available only to instances connected to a particular OpenStack-defined network.

3.3.7 Share Server

A share server is a logical entity that manages the shares that are created on a specific share network. Depending on the implementation of a specific Manila driver, a share server may be a configuration object within the storage controller, or it may represent logical resources provisioned within an OpenStack deployment that are used to support the data path used to access Manila shares.

Share servers interact with network services to determine the appropriate IP addresses on which to export shares according to the related share network. Manila has a pluggable network model that allows share servers to work with OpenStack environments that have either Nova-Network or Neutron deployed.

3.4 Manila network plugins

A network plugin is used to provide network resources to the manila-share service. There are a set of network plugins that provide for a variety of integration approaches with the network services that are available with OpenStack. The network plugin is chosen by setting the value of the `network_api_class` configuration option within the driver-specific stanza of the Manila configuration file, found under the name of `manila.conf`. It is worth mentioning that a network plugin is needed only when the Manila service handles the share servers.

3.4.1 Standalone Network Plugin

The Standalone Network plugin is meant to be simple and not rely on anything outside of the Manila service. The plugin allows the administrator to specify the details of an existing network to which a storage controller is connected. In order to select the standalone network plugin, the following options should be added to the driver-specific stanza within the configuration file:

```
network_api_class = manila.network.StandaloneNetworkPlugin
standalone_network_plugin_allowed_ip_ranges = 10.0.0.2 - 10.0.0.254
standalone_network_plugin_ip_version = 4
standalone_network_plugin_segmentation_id = 314
standalone_network_plugin_mask = 255.255.255.0
standalone_network_plugin_gateway = 10.0.0.1
```

3.4.2 Nova Network Plugin

The Nova-Network plugin offers support for more complex network operations, such as flat networks or VLAN-segmented networks. The plugin can function in two ways, working either with a single network, which is provided in the configuration file, or multiple networks, being more configurable.

In case the single Nova Network Plugin is desired, the following should be placed under the driver-specific stanza within the configuration file:

```
network_api_class = manila.network.NovaSingleNetworkPlugin
nova_single_network_plugin_net_id = 97fb9f7e-4ffe-4900-8dba-c6d4251e588e
```

In case the configurable Nova Network Plugin is chosen, only a single option should be added to the driver-specific stanza in the configuration file:

```
network_api_class=manila.network.NovaNetworkPlugin
```

3.4.3 Neutron Network Plugin

The Neutron Network plugin is the most capable network plugin, offering many features, such as flat networks, VLAN networks, VXLAN networks and GRE tunneling. In order to use this specific plugin, the following options should be added to the driver-specific stanza within the Manila configuration file:

```
network_api_class = manila.network.NeutronNetworkPlugin
neutron_net_id = 37fb9f7e-4ffe-4900-8dba-c6d4251e588e
neutron_subnet_id = 447732be-4cf2-42b0-83dc-4b6f4ed5368c
```

3.5 Manila CLI

The Manila service provides an API for the operations it is able to perform. Calling these operations can be done either via the CLI (Command Line Interface) or, as it will be presented later, using the Manila Web GUI from the OpenStack dashboard. Below, the most commonly used operations will be presented and described in a few words.

Operation	CLI Command	Description
Create	<code>manila create <protocol> <size></code>	creates a new share with the given size, using either the NFS or CIFS protocol
Delete	<code>manila delete <share></code>	deletes the specified share
List	<code>manila list</code>	lists all shares
Show	<code>manila show <share></code>	displays information about the specified share
Update	<code>manila update <share></code>	updates various information of the specified share
Reset	<code>manila reset-state <share></code>	resets the status of the specified share (defaults to available)
Force Delete	<code>manila force-delete <share></code>	attempts to force-delete the specified share, regardless of state

Access Allow	<code>manila access-allow <share> <access_type> <access_to></code>	allow access to the specified share, using the given access type to the mentioned entity
Access Deny	<code>manila access-deny <share> <access_rule_id></code>	delete the given access rule for the specified share
Access List	<code>manila access-list <share></code>	display access rules for the specified share
Type Create	<code>manila type-create <name> <handles_share_server></code>	creates a new share type with provided name and handle share server flag
Type Delete	<code>manila type-delete <type_id></code>	delete the given share type
Type List	<code>manila type-list</code>	displays all share types

4 Deployment of OpenStack

This section describes the steps underwent in order to install both OpenStack and OpenStack Manila and the configuration needed to make the Manila service work with an underlying OpenStack installation. The instructions presented in this section assume the installation of the OpenStack Kilo release on CERN CentOS 7 operating system.

4.1 Using Packstack to install OpenStack

Packstack is a utility that uses Puppet modules to deploy various parts of OpenStack on multiple pre-installed servers over SSH automatically. Currently only Fedora, Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) and compatible derivatives of both are supported.

To begin the installation, the repository protection has to be disabled first. This can be done by changing the value of the `enabled` field from 1 to 0 in `/etc/yum/pluginconf.d/protectbase.conf`.

```
sudo sed -i 's/1/0/g' /etc/yum/pluginconf.d/protectbase.conf
```

Next, update the repositories and install packstack.

```
sudo yum update -y
sudo yum install -y openstack-packstack
```

Finally, use packstack to install OpenStack, but without the Neutron component.

```
sudo packstack -allinone -os-neutron-install=n
```

Last thing needed is to make a small change in Nova Network. In the `/usr/lib/python2.7/site-packages/nova/network/linux_net.py`, change the following line and then restart the nova network service.

```
if interface:      →   if interface and interface != 'lo':
sudo systemctl restart openstack-nova-network
```

4.2 Manila integration

In this section, the process of installing, configuring and linking OpenStack Manila to other OpenStack services will be explained. The installation of the file sharing service can be done either manually or by using various automated deployment tools such as Packstack or DevStack.

4.2.1 Step-by-step install guide

This section describes how to manually install OpenStack Manila and do the appropriate configuring.

Manila binaries may be installed using various distribution packages or from source code. The latter case will be explained, namely, installation by cloning a git repository:

```
git clone -b stable/kilo https://github.com/openstack/manila
```

Run the installation script from the newly created ‘manila’ directory:

```
sudo python setup.py install
```

Next step is to install the Manila client. This is the binary that will be used for issuing manila requests:

```
sudo pip install python-manilaclient>=1.0.4
```

After the binaries have been installed, Manila should be registered with Keystone. In order to do that, a service user will be created and the admin role must be provided to said user:

```
openstack user create --password-prompt manila
openstack role add --project service --user manila admin
```

After the Manila service user has been created, the Manila service entities need to be created in keystone, along with the service API endpoints:

```
openstack service create \
  --name manila \
  --description "OpenStack Shared Filesystems" \
  share
openstack endpoint create \
  --publicurl http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s \
  --internalurl http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s \
  --adminurl http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s \
  --region regionOne \
  share
```

Property	Value
description	OpenStack Shared Filesystems
enabled	True
id	4c13e9ff7ec04f4e95a26f72ecdf9919
name	manila
type	share

Figure 3 OpenStack service create

Property	Value
adminurl	http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s
id	c1984777db6941919657d15b25f05c94
internalurl	http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s
publicurl	http://controller:8786/v1/%(tenant_id)s
region	regionOne
service_id	4c13e9ff7ec04f4e95a26f72ecdf9919

Figure 4 OpenStack endpoint create

Port 8787 is the default port for Manila. It can be changed to any other port, as long as this change is also reflected in the configuration file, under the `osapi_share_listen_port` property.

The ‘controller’ from the keystone endpoint URLs represent the machine where the keystone service is located and should be replaced with the appropriate IP address or host name, if the DNS is aware of it.

Following step is the preparation of the configuration file. Copy the following files from the ‘%git_directory%/etc/manila’ to ‘/etc/manila’:

```
policy.json
api-paste.ini
rootwrap.conf
rootwrap.d/share.filters
```

```
cd manila/etc/manila/  
sudo cp policy.json api-paste.ini rootwrap.conf  
rootwrap.d/share.filters /etc/manila/
```

The configuration file will be generated using tox by running the following command:

```
tox -e genconfig
```

This will create a new file called manila.conf.sample. Remove the '.sample' suffix and copy it into the '/etc/manila/ directory':

```
sudo cp manila.conf.sample /etc/manila/manila.conf
```

Next step is to create the manila user in the database and create a dedicated database for this service. It is assumed that the MySQL database has already been installed.

```
sudo mysql -u root -p  
CREATE DATABASE manila;  
GRANT ALL PRIVILEGES ON manila.* TO 'manila'@'localhost' \  
IDENTIFIED BY 'MANILA_DBPASS';  
GRANT ALL PRIVILEGES ON manila.* TO 'manila'@'%' \  
IDENTIFIED BY 'MANILA_DBPASS';  
EXIT;
```

Create Manila's tables and apply all migrations:

```
manila-manage db sync
```

Create the log files now (this step assumes you already have a manila user account):

```
sudo mkdir /var/log/manila/  
touch /var/log/manila/api.log /var/log/manila/scheduler.log  
/var/log/manila/share.log  
chown -R manila:manila /var/log/manila/  
chmod 755 /var/log/manila/  
chmod 644 /var/log/manila/*
```

Last step is creating the services scripts and linking them to systemctl. A new file will be created for the three main Manila services with the following content:

```
sudo touch /usr/lib/systemd/system/openstack-manila-api.service  
  
[Unit]  
Description=OpenStack Manila API Server  
After=syslog.target network.target  
  
[Service]  
Type=simple  
User=manila  
ExecStart=/usr/bin/manila-api --config-file /usr/share/manila/manila-dist.conf  
--config-file /etc/manila/manila.conf --logfile /var/log/manila/api.log  
  
[Install]  
WantedBy=multi-user.target
```

```

sudo touch /usr/lib/systemd/system/openstack-manila-scheduler.service

[Unit]
Description=OpenStack Manila Scheduler
After=syslog.target network.target

[Service]
Type=simple
User=manila
ExecStart=/usr/bin/manila-scheduler --config-file /usr/share/manila/manila-
dist.conf --config-file /etc/manila/manila.conf --logfile
/var/log/manila/scheduler.log

[Install]
WantedBy=multi-user.target

```

```

sudo touch /usr/lib/systemd/system/openstack-manila-share.service

[Unit]
Description=OpenStack Manila Share Service
After=syslog.target network.target

[Service]
Type=simple
User=manila
ExecStart=/usr/bin/manila-share --config-file /usr/share/manila/manila-
dist.conf --config-file /etc/manila/manila.conf --logfile
/var/log/manila/share.log

[Install]
WantedBy=multi-user.target

```

The only thing left now is to enable and start the services:

```

sudo systemctl enable openstack-manila-api
sudo systemctl enable openstack-manila-scheduler
sudo systemctl enable openstack-manila-share
sudo systemctl start openstack-manila-api openstack-manila-scheduler
openstack-manila-share

```

4.2.2 Configuration file

Upon installation, the Manila service must be configured. Below will be listed the configuration parameters that need to be set. However, the backend driver stanza will not be described here.

```

[DEFAULT]
...
api_paste_config = /etc/manila/api-paste.ini
state_path /var/lib/manila
default_share_type = %default_share_type% (must be created)
rootwrap_config = /etc/manila/rootwrap.conf
enabled_share_backends = %list of backends%
nova_catalog_info = compute:nova:publicURL
nova_catalog_admin_info = compute:nova:adminURL
nova_admin_username = %nova_admin_username% (Generic driver requires Nova service)
nova_admin_password = %nova_admin_password%
nova_admin_tenant_name = %nova_admin_tenant_name%
nova_admin_auth_url = % nova_admin_auth_url%
verbose = true

```

```
log_dir = /var/log/manila
osapi_share_listen = 0.0.0.0
cinder_catalog_info = volume:cinder:publicURL
cinder_admin_username = %cinder_admin_username% (Generic driver requires Cinder service)
cinder_admin_password = %cinder_admin_password%
cinder_admin_tenant = %cinder_admin_tenant%
cinder_admin_auth_url = %cinder_admin_auth_url%
cinder_volume_type = %cinder_volume_type_id%

[database]
...
connection = mysql://manila:%MANILA_DBPASS%@%DB_HOST%/manila

[keystone_authtoken]
...
auth_uri = %public_identity_endpoint% (e.g. https://keystonedev.cern.ch/main)
signing_dir = /var/cache/manila
auth_protocol = %auth_protocol% (http or https)
identity_uri = %admin_identity_endpoint% (e.g. https://keystonedev.cern.ch/main)
admin_user = %admin_user%
admin_password = %admin_password%
admin_tenant_name = %admin_tenant_name%

[oslo_concurrency]
...
lock_path = /tmp/manila/manila_locks

[oslo_messaging_rabbit]
...
rabbit_host = %rabbit_host%
rabbit_port = %rabbit_port%
rabbit_hosts = %rabbit_host:rabbit_port%
rabbit_use_ssl = false
rabbit_userid = guest
rabbit_password = guest
rabbit_virtual_host = /
rabbit_ha_queues = false
```

4.2.3 Using Packstack to install Manila

Installing the Manila component using Packstack can be done with a fresh installation of OpenStack, in this case inserting a new parameter to the packstack install command, such as:

```
sudo packstack --allinone -os-manila-install=y
```

The installation can be done afterwards as well, on top of an already existing OpenStack, assuming there is a Packstack answer file with the `CONFIG_MANILA_INSTALL=y` field set.

```
sudo packstack --answer-file=%answer_file%
```

4.2.4 Manila-UI plugin for Horizon

OpenStack Manila also provides a plugin for Horizon, in order to have access to a web interface. In order to apply the web UI plugin, the Horizon and Manila-UI repositories must be obtained:

```
git clone https://github.com/openstack/horizon
git clone https://github.com/openstack/manila-ui
```

Afterwards, create a virtual environment and install the Horizon dependencies:

```
cd horizon
python tools/install_venv.py
```

Set up your `local_settings.py` file:

```
cp openstack_dashboard/local/local_settings.py.example
openstack_dashboard/local/local_settings.py
```

Open up the copied `local_settings.py` file and verify that `OPENSTACK_HOST`, `OPENSTACK_KEYSTONE_URL` and `OPENSTACK_KEYSTONE_DEFAULT_ROLE` settings are correct for your environment. In the `HORIZON_CONFIG` definition, insert the following line at the end:

```
'customization_module': 'manila_ui.overrides',
```

Install Manila UI dependencies in your virtual environment:

```
tools/with_venv.sh pip install -e ../manila-ui/
```

Afterwards, enable it in Horizon:

```
cp ../manila-ui/manila_ui/enabled/_90_manila_*.py
openstack_dashboard/local/enabled
```

In order to start the application, run the following command:

```
./run_tests.sh --runserver 0.0.0.0:8080
```

The application will now run on `http://localhost:8080/`.

5 Manila implementation

The Manila implementation that has been done as part of the project uses the Generic driver. This driver relies only on services found within OpenStack and this approach has proven favorable because it allows getting a better understand on how the service functions whilst at the same time not relying on proprietary or complex backends.

5.1 Generic driver - handling share servers

When the generic driver has the option of handling the share servers activated, this means that it will take care of creating new VMs in order to provision shares. When a share is issued, a new VM is launched and a volume is attached to the VM. The great advantage of this method is that it provides a scalable system with no single point of failure. The disadvantage is that the resource usage might not be optimal.

Figure 5 Generic driver - no single point of failure

If the driver is configured to handle its own servers, a network plugin may be required. However, the generic driver does not use any network plugins although other drivers might. An image from which the VM will boot must also be provided, along with login credentials. Below can be found the stanza for a backend using the generic driver that is handling its own share servers:

```
[backend_handle_share_servers]
share_driver = manila.share.drivers.generic.GenericShareDriver
driver_handles_share_servers = true
share_backend_name = handle_share_servers
service_instance_user = ubuntu
service_instance_passwod = ubuntu
service_image_name = ubuntu_image_name
path_to_private_key = ~/.ssh/id_rsa
path_to_public_key = ~/.ssh/id_rsa.pub
```

5.2 Generic driver - not handling share servers

When the generic driver functions without handling the share servers it needs to be provided the address of an already existing and configured server. The provided server should have NFS and Samba servers installed, with the mention that Samba must be set to work with registry-based configuration.

The generic driver only interacts with the provided server and for every share issued, it creates a new volume and attaches it to the server. The advantage of this method is greater control of the share server for the system administrator and less resource usage, but at the same time it is not as scalable.

Figure 6 Generic driver - single point of failure

This is the driver method of functioning that has been chosen to be integrated with the CERN's Private Cloud existing OpenStack services in order to test the Manila deployment with dependencies upon the production services.

Some parameters are required in the configuration file, such as address of the provided share server, along with login credentials. Below can be found the stanza for a backend using the generic driver while not handling its own share servers.

```
[backend_not_handle_share_servers]
share_driver = manila.share.drivers.generic.GenericShareDriver
driver_handles_share_servers = false
share_backend_name = not_handle_share_servers
service_instance_user = ubuntu
service_instance_passwod = ubuntu
service_instance_name_or_id = share_server_name_or_id
path_to_private_key = ~/.ssh/id_rsa
path_to_public_key = ~/.ssh/id_rsa.pub
```

5.3 Creating shares

In order to create a share, a share type must be provided. This can either be specified at the instruction level or a default type be set in the configuration file, under the `default_share_type` parameter.

Creating a new share type is done by the following command, passing the name of the share type and whether it should handle share servers or not:

```
manila type-create <name> <spec_driver_handles_share_servers>
```

To create a share, the following command is set with a given protocol (be it NFS or CIFS), a size in GBs and optionally, a name and a specific share-type, otherwise the default one will be used:

```
manila create <protocol> <size> -- name <name> -- share-type <type>
```

Upon creating a share, access must be permitted to it. This is done by specifying the share in question, the type of access (IP, user or cert) and the value to whom access is given to:

```
manila access-allow <share> <access_type> <access_to>
```

Now the share can be mounted and accessed.

6 Debugging information

This section is meant to provide some useful information about how to proceed when a share does not succeed. Some known issues are also explained and a workaround is provided for dealing with such matters.

6.1 Status of a share

The status of a share can be seen using the `manila list` or `manila show <share>` command. These constitute the primary means of checking the status of a share. If the share is found in the `error` or `error_deleting` state, more information can be found by checking the log files, most commonly found at `/var/log/manila/`, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the configuration file.

6.2 Mounting NFS shares with caching enabled

In case of mounting a NFS share with caching enabled, it is known of an issue where sometimes files stay cached and do not appear on the server side or to other clients using the same share only after a given period of time. If this is to be avoided at all costs, mounting the share can be done without caching, as shown in the example below:

```
mount -o noac %export_location% %mount_location%
```

6.3 Device mapping inconsistency

In case of a KVM hypervisor under CentOS 6, sometime there is an inconsistency when mounting a new volume between the device path provided by the hypervisor to the Nova service and the device path actually found inside the VM. This will affect Manila share operations as they rely on the device path provided by the nova service, which is in fact the one the received from the hypervisor.

This can be solved by mounting based on the `/dev/disk/by-id/` path instead of the one provided. The files in this path have a standard name, `'virtio-'` followed by the first 20 characters of the volume's ID string (e.g. `virtio-3f0dbd9f-e347-400c-a`) and they map to the correct device disk. This workaround of this problem has been adding a new method in the Manila's generic driver code to return the correct `'/dev/disk/by-id/'` device name and use this one for all further operations.

```
def _get_volume_mountpoint(self, volume_id):
    """Returns the volume's mount point using the /dev/disk/by-id link,
    as opposed to using the volume['mountpoint'] property.

    :param volume_id: volume identifier
    :return: volume mount point by id
    """
    if not volume_id or len(volume_id) < 20:
        raise exception.ManilaException(_("Invalid volume-id provided."))

    return "/dev/disk/by-id/virtio-" + volume_id[:20]
```

7 Conclusions

The OpenStack Manila service offers an elegant way of share provisioning to its users. The system is keeping in line with the other OpenStack components, thus making the CLI simple and easy to use. With the help of network plugins, access to the shares can be even better controlled by taking benefit of share networks.

The service can also function on its own or in conjunction with other systems. This is due to the architecture on which it relies. By using a driver between the share service and the storage backend, a needed level of decoupling is being offered. At the same time, this solution also allows for a variety of storage backends to be used with the Manila service.

As has been tested, the service can be integrated and made to work with CERN's Private Cloud OpenStack deployment. Because there is interest to offer users the chance to provision their own shares, it is hoped that a more suitable backend solution can be integrated with the Manila service, thus effectively enabling 'Shares-as-a-Service' in the Private Cloud.

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